

TO STUDY THE ROLE AND EFFICACY OF CELL BLOCK ON EFFUSION FLUID COMPARED TO DIRECT SMEARS

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Received: May 04, 2025

Accepted: Jun 05, 2025

Published: Jun 06, 2025

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND

Effusion fluids examination through the cytopathologically diagnostic of cellular level of reactive mesothelial cells, malignancy, benign and any type of body inflammation screening and routinely processing. Direct smears is not accurate reasult in effusion fluids and best for cell block examination cellular morphology, Cellularity. The morphologically of cellularity were good help by direct smears and cell block as compared to direct smears, Contributaion accurate diagnosis on effusion fluids.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our study was prospective taken from hospital based & no. Cases were 113 both in patient and out patient department of cytopathology in NIMS hospital rajasthan,jaipur,India.Study period:1st January 2025 to 30th May 2025.

RESULTS

Effusion fluid sensitivity direct smears was (33.65%) and cell block was (24.68%-43.58%), specificity direct smears was examination (88.89%) and cell block was (51.75%-99.72%), Positive predictive value of direct smear examination (97.22%) and when cell block was (84.39%-99.56%), Negative predictive value of direct examination was (10.39%) and when cell block was (8.14%-13.17%) and accuracy of direct smear of (38.05%) compared to cell block was (29.08%-47.67%).

CONCLUSION

Direct smears view under microscope overlapping and distribution of cells, a lot of time consumable examination and when Cell block process through short field of microscope high cellularity same specimen for direct smears. Using cell block give better confidentiality in reporting the malignancy and future study preserving long duration without loss of cellular component,Architectural as a histopathological block.

KEY WORDS

Cell block, Direct smears, Effusion body fluids.

INTRODUCTION

Cell block technique widely used from many years back and now for advised to follow technique specimen remaining amount⁽¹⁾.

The cell block technique, a conventional method utilizing cytocentrifugation and fine-needle aspiration cytology, is essential for identifying malignant cells by enhancing cellular morphology and cellularity⁽²⁾. Various techniques exist for processing cell blocks with effusion samples often collected in sterile containers or tubes⁽³⁾. The needle is inserted into peritoneal/pleural/pericardial space with aspiration of effusion, facilitating early cytological examination, which is especially beneficial for the early detection of cellular abnormalities, including malignancies. Smears are routinely

stained and examined under a microscopy by a trained cytopathologist. Cell blocks also be made for all samples received⁽⁴⁾. This technique aids in identifying inflammatory, cancerous and non-cancerous cells. For diagnostic accuracy adequate cell volume is essential, ensuring minimal artifacts in the results⁽⁵⁾. For cell block 10% formalin solution is commonly used in manual method⁽⁶⁾.

In cell block technique sedimented fluid material into few drops plasma, thrombin and then ready clot from specimen. As per treated with fixative and routinely perform as a biopsy specimen⁽⁷⁾. Specific examination find out for stains like Z-N, Periodic Acid-Schiff, Gomori-Methenamine silver nitrate routine processing cell block cutting section⁽⁸⁾. Cell block exist cells in alcoholic fixatives papinicolous stains smears, nuclear and cytoplasmic ratio enough kept and immunostaining also simple⁽⁹⁾. It is very important examination of cytopathology regions is that tissue examination similarly and further study for immunohistochemical analysis⁽¹⁰⁾. Handling of cell block technique not new now, it is a specimen treated manualing step considers loss of material⁽¹¹⁾. In direct smears preparation principally processing blood clot separated and sedimented material obtain and in this cellular and shapes, sizes also not affected⁽¹²⁾.

The abnormal accumulation of fluid in body cavities, often caused by pathological condition such as infections, inflammation, benign and malignant tumors requires careful evaluation for accurate diagnosis. Cytopathological techniques are essential in determining the root causes of these fluid buildups. Both approaches aid in the early identification and treatment of underlying illnesses⁽¹³⁾. Effusion fluids undergo initial observational examinations for color, appearance, odour and viscosity which provide diagnostic insight. For malignancies like adenocarcinoma, Cancer of the squamous cell, malignant melanoma, etc. Immunocytochemistry and molecular study can also be carried-out effectively on effusion fluids.

A lack of cell volume or improper cytopspin procedures can lead to false negative, concealing clinically relevant abnormalities.

For optional diagnostic accuracy, cell blocks provide a reliable method to minimize artifacts and accurately assess cell morphology. By allowing for large cell volumes on a concentrated slide area, cell blocks enable pathologists to deliver more precise results and enhance the diagnostic pathway⁽¹⁴⁾.

The effusion fluids examination detection malignancy and staging malignancy disease. It is important for identify two between malignancy and benign effusions, indicative of patient prognosis treatment⁽¹⁵⁾.

Worldwide most commonly affected liver cirrhosis causing by ascites⁽¹⁶⁾. Investigation of ascites specimen for analysis fluid routinely perform biochemical test and non-biochemical test, microbial culture, leukocytes count, cytology⁽¹⁷⁾.

The examination of direct smears in routine cytology study of fluid often yields low accuracy due to overlapping cells on the smears. In contrast, the cell block technique provides higher accuracy by preserving cellular architecture and discontinued the use of direct smears in favor of the cell block⁽¹⁸⁾.

Conventional cytological slide smears, routinely uses technique and other technique body fluid analysis through cell block technique this technique unawareness about advantages diagnostic contribution⁽¹⁹⁾. In this processing lacking of cellular population and morphological and oversuspended of cells. For both epithelial cell malignant and reactive benign One of the diagnostic challenges with traditional smears is mesothelial cells. Cell block method same specimen multiple section cutting and many stains using for diagnostic diseases purposes and advantages of good architecture as it is for long period of times further examination purposes and immunohistochemistry(IHC)⁽²⁰⁾.

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY: Plasma thrombin method and direct smear's examination.

DIRECT SMEAR'S PREPARATION: (10-20ml) fluid was taken into reya vial and centrifuged at 1500 RPM between 7-8 minutes. Then supernatant part was discarded. The sediment was used to make 4 smears, which includes, One dry smear, One dry cell button (cytopsin centrifugated), One wet smear (95% ethenol fixed) and One wet (95% ethenol fixed) cell button. After that staining procedure was performed. Four commonly stains near used for staining the smear in cytopathology.

(A) PAP (Papnicolous) Staining.

(B) H and E (Hematoxyline and Eosin) Staining.

(C) MGG (May gruenwald's Geimsa) Staining.

(D) Leishman Staining.

Figure no.1: Processing of specimen (DR.Pranab dey)²¹

Procedure of Haematoxyline and Eosin Staining

- Haematoxyline: 5-8 minutes.
- Running tap water: 3-5 minutes.
- Eosin stain : 1 minutes.
- AcetoneI : 2 minutes.
- AcetoneII: 2 minutes.
- XyleneI : 2 minutes.
- XyleneII : 2 minutes.
- Air dry , mount with D.P.X and slide covered with cover slip.
- Microscopic examination.

Figure no.4 ;H and E Stain Reagents

PREPARATION OF CELL BLOCK: Fluid was taken into reya vial and centrifuged at 1500 RPM for 15 minutes. After supernatant part was discarded, sedimented part was fixed in 10% formalin and kept at room temperature for four hours, After that discard the fixatives liquid and add 100 μ l citrate plasma and 200 μ l of uniplastin plasma was mixed and centrifuged at 1500 RPM for two minutes. Collect solid material (clot) into filter paper (wattsman) for tissue processing.

Figure no.7:Cell block preparation(Dr.Pranab Dey)²¹

Procedures of Haematoxyline and Eosin staining

- Depparafinizes Section
- Xylene for : 2 minutes
- Xylene for : 2 minutes
- Xylene for : 2 minutes
- 100% Acetone for : 2 minutes
- 80% Acetone for : 2 minutes
- 70% Acetone for : 2 minutes

- Running tap water for :5-8 minutes
- Haematoxyline stain for : 5-8 minutes
- Running tap water for : 5-6 minutes
- Eosin stain for : 1 minutes
- 70% Acetone for : 2 minutes
- 80% Acetone for : 2 minutes
- 100% Acetone for : 2 minutes
- Xylene for : 2 minutes
- Xylene for : 2 minutes
- Air dry, Mount with D.P.X and slide covered with cover slip.
- Microscopic examination

Figures 13: Malignancy seen under microscope

RESULTS

In this study of 113 samples were taken, between 30- 70 years. Minimum age was \leq 30 years patients 7.08%(8/113) of cases, patients 31-40 years were 14.16% (16/113) 41-50 years were patients 19.47% (22/113), 51-60 years 19.47% (22/113), Highly frequency were age 61-70 years 23.89% (27/113) and remaining of patient >70 years 15.93% (18/113).

Table 1: Age distribution frequency of patients

Interval by age	n = 113	In %
\leq 30 Yrs.	8	7.08%
31 - 40 Yrs.	16	14.16%
41 - 50 Yrs.	22	19.47%
51 - 60 Yrs.	22	19.47%
61 - 70 Yrs.	27	23.89%
> 70	18	15.93%

Graph no .1: Age distribution frequency of patients

In this study found in 65.49% were males (74/113) and 34.51% (39/113) were females patients.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of gender of patients

Gender	n = 113	In %
Male	74	65.49%
Female	39	34.51%

Graph no. 2: Frequency distribution of gender of patients

Total number of specimen types processing pleural fluid 55.75% (63/113) most largest number, ascitic fluid was 39.82%(45/113) and pericardial fluid was 3.54%(4/113).

Table 3: Frequency distribution of specimens

Specimens	n = 113	In %
PLEURAL FLUID	63	55.75%
ASCITIC FLUID	46	40.71%
PERICARDIAL FLUID	4	3.54%

Graph no. 4: Frequency distribution of specimens

In this study results found in patient totally 113 cases in benign 68.14% (77/113) and malignant 23.89% (27/113), Inconclusion 7.93% (9/113).

Table 4: Incidence of benign & malignancy in patients

Category	n = 113	In %
Benign	77	68.14%
Malignant	27	23.89%
Inconclusive	9	7.96%

Graph no. 4: Incidence of benign & malignancy in patients

According to table number 5 efficacy of cell block over direct smears examination on effusion fluid sensitivity direct smear was (33.65%) and cell block was (24.68%-43.58%), specificity direct smears was examination (88.89%) and cell block was (51.75%-99.72%), Positive likelihood ratio of direct smears was (3.03) and cell block was (0.47-19.6), direct smears was Negative likelihood ratio (0.75) and cell block was (0.57-0.98), Positive predictive value of direct smear examination (97.22%) and when cell block was (84.39%-99.56%), Negative predictive value of direct examination was (10.39%) and when cell block is (8.14%-13.17%) and accuracy of direct smear of (38.05%) compared to cell block was (29.08%-47.67%).

Table 5: Efficacy of cell block compared to direct smear on effusion fluid

Characteristics	Value	95% Confidence Interval
Sensitivity	33.65%	24.68% - 43.58%
Specificity	88.89%	51.75% - 99.72%
Positive Likelihood Ratio	3.03	0.47 - 19.6
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.75	0.57 - 0.98
Positive Predictive Value	97.22%	84.39% - 99.56%
Negative Predictive Value	10.39%	8.14% - 13.17%
Accuracy	38.05%	29.08% - 47.67%

In this found of Descriptive statistics of patient age of patient minimum 9 ,maximum 87,median 55(44-66) and 53.87 ± 16 .

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of age of patients

Minimum	Maximum	Median (IQR)	Mean \pm SD
9	87	55 (44-66)	53.87 ± 16

Malignant 27 cases out of in ICC was done in 12 case

Table 7: ICC Report of positive cases

Category	Positive Cases	ICC Report
Malignant	27	12

DISCUSSION

In this study body effusions fluid are processed by using routine direct smears and cell block technique of pleural, ascitic and pericardial. Total 113 cases of various sites of body fluids were received. In this investigation, in the various fluids was malignancy 27 (23.89%) and benign in 77 (68.14%) of cases. Patient age of effusion fluids between (<30- 70> years). Similar findings were observed by Bindu et al⁽²²⁾ In this study majority of specimen pleural fluid(55.75%), Ascitic fluid (39.82%), Pericardial fluid (3.54%) similar to majority of specimen done by BM et al⁽²³⁾ have done as use of specimen pleural fluid(53%), Ascitic fluid (46%). Benign (68.14%), Confirmed as malignancy(23%) was through the cell block and (7.96%) inconclusion due to not contribution of cell block processing region was lack of sedimented material. Similar study by Dr. Akhila puskuru and manoj patrni⁽²⁴⁾ Benign(74%) and Malignancy (26%), Slightly lower percentage due to sample size less compared to present study. The sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value (NPV), and positive predictive value (PPV) of direct smears on effusion fluid for identifying malignancy were reported in this study as 33.65%, 88.89%, 10.39%, and 97.22%, respectively. Matreja, et al.⁽²⁵⁾ have done The sensitivity, specificity, NPV and positive predictive value (PPV) of direct smears for diagnosing cancer were reported as 69.2%, 95%, 56.25%, and 97.1%, respectively. In this study sensitivity(24.68% - 43.58%), specificity(51.75% - 99.72%), Negative Predictive value(8.14% - 13.17%) and positive predictive value (84.39% - 99.56%) of cell block on effusion fluid for diagnosing malignancy was reported as followed. Matreja, et al.⁽²⁵⁾, sensitivity(92.3%), specificity(99.2%), Negative Predictive value(99.28%), positive predictive value (92.3%) and of CB were 99.2%, 92.3% and 99.28%, respectively in the index study, which were greater than that for CS.

Malignant 27 cases out of in ICC 12 cases was Positive in similar study in ICC have done by MN Nowsher *et al*²⁶. Five positive cases of ICC. My study ICC positivity higher due to sample size and malignancy higher than.

SUMMARY

In this study, 113 effusion fluids specimen was examination through direct smears and cell block from 10 January to 30 May in department of cytology in NIMS hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan.

1. Out of 113 effusion fluids, pleural fluid was 63(55.75%), Ascitic fluid was 46(40.7%), and Pericardial fluids was 4(3.54%).

2. Out of 113 studied, 74 cases (65.49%) were male and 39 cases (34.51%) were female, Male: Female ratio was 1.89:1 .

3. In my research accuracy of direct smears is 38.05% and when cell block is 29.08%-47.67%.

4. Direct smears is not accurate result in effusion fluids and best for cell block examination cellular morphology, cellularity.

5. The morphologically of cellularity were good help by direct smears and cell block as compared to direct smears, contribution accurate diagnosis on effusion fluids.

CONCLUSION

In this study direct smears through the examination accuracy, morphology, nuclear and cytoplasm ratio etc, better as compared to cell block increasing diagnostic purpose for good treatment for effusion body fluids. Direct smears view under microscope overlapping and distribution of cells, a lot of time consumable examination and when Cell block process through short field of microscope high cellularity same specimen for direct smears. Using cell block give better confidentiality in reporting the malignancy and future study preserving long duration without loss of cellular component, Architectural as a histopathological block. Cell block with immunocytochemistry serves as the best way to diagnose malignancy, especially in cases with unknown primary.

1. Koss LG: Diagnostic Cytology and Its Histopathologic Bases. Fifth edition. Philadelphia, Lippincott Williams and Wilkins. Pennsylvania. USA. 2006 Pg 919-1018
2. Gupta N, Sekar A, Rajwanshi A. Role of FNAC, fluid specimens, and cell blocks for cytological diagnosis of lung cancer in the present era. *J Cytol* 2015;32:217-22.
3. Tommola, E.; Kalfert, D.; Hakso-Makinen, et al. The Contributory Role of Cell Blocks in Salivary Gland Neoplasm Fine Needle Aspirations Classified by the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytology. *Diagnostics* 2021,11,1778.
4. Caudhary N, Das S, Sinha S. Comparative evaluation of diagnostic efficacy of cell block versus aspiration cytology. *Adv Hum Biol* 2023;13:130-4.
5. Dr. S.S. Sabita Rani, H.No:30-2-701/A, West City, Kazipet, Madikonda 506142, Warangal Urban, Telangana State, India.
6. Shidham VB and Epple J. Collection and processing of effusion fluids for cytopathologic evaluation. *CytoJournal* 2022;19:5.
7. De. Girolami E. Applications of plasma thrombin cell block in diagnostic cytology. Part II. Digestive and Respiratory Tracts, Breast and Effusions. *Annu Pathol* 1997,12: 91-110.
8. Leung SW, Bedard YC. Methods in Pathology. Simple mini block technique for cytology. *Mod pathol* 1993;6(5):630-632.
9. Jing X, Li QK, Bedrossian U, Michael CW. Morphologic and Immunohistochemical performances of effusion cell blocks prepared using 3 different methods. *Am J Clin Pathol* 2013;139:177-82.
10. Yang GC, Wan LS, Papellas J, Waisman J. Compact cell blocks, Use for body fluid, Fine needle aspirations and Endometrial brush biopsies. *Acta Cytol* 1998; 42: 703-706.
11. Koss LG: Diagnostic Cytology and Its Histopathologic Bases. Fifth edition. Philadelphia, Lippincott Williams and Wilkins. Pennsylvania. USA. 2006 Pg 919-1018
12. De. Girolami E. Applications of plasma thrombin cell block in diagnostic cytology. Part II. Digestive and Respiratory Tracts, Breast and Effusions. *Annu Pathol* 1997,12: 91-110.
13. Dr. Teena MURTHY at bldu university in 2017. comparative study of conventional smears and cell block on body fluid cytology digitallibrary.bldeu.ac.in.

14. Mahendra singh,Lubna khan,Yogendra N.Verma, et al “Comparative study for the use of different techniques in serous fluid cytology”.journal of evolution of medical and dental sciences 2015;vol.4,issue18,march02;page3154-3161,DOI:10.14260/jemds2015/456.
15. Bernard N. Pleural, peritoneal and pericardial effusion. In: Bibbo M, Wilbur DC, editors. Comprehensive cytopathology. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Saunders, Elsevier, 2008, 515.
16. Runyon BA. Management of adult patients with ascites caused by cirrhosis. Hepatology 2004;39:841-56.
17. Tarn AC, Lapworth R. Biochemical analysis of ascitic (peritoneal) fluid: What should we measure? Ann Clin Biochem 2010;47:397-407
18. Thapar M.Mishra RK,Sharma A,Goyal V,Goyal V.Critical analysis of cell block versus smear examination in effusion.J Cytol.2009;26:60-4.
- 21.Kumar SH, Sudhamani S, Shetty D, Rajiv R. Clinicopathological study of 117 body fluids: Comparison of conventional smear and cell block. Curr Health Sci J 2020;46:336-43.
19. Pal S, Murmu D, Goswami BK. Ascitic fluid cytology in suspected malignant effusions with special emphasis on cell block preparation. J Evol Med Dent Sci 2015;4:10488-94.
20. Dr.Prnab dey. SBN 978-981-10-8251-1 ISBN 978-981-10-8252-8 (eBook)
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8252-8> Library of Congress Control Number: 2018941817
21. Bindu, et al.Medical Journal of Dr. D.Y. Patil Vidyapeeth | Volume 17 | Issue 4 | July-August 2024 Website:<https://journals.lww.com/mjdy>
DOI:10.4103/mjdrdypu.mjdrdypu_243_23
22. Viral BM *et al.* Analysis of diagnostic value of cytological smear method versus cell block method in body fluid cytology: study of 150 cases. Ethiop J Health Sci 2014;24:125-30.
23. Dr.Akhila puskuru and manoj patruni International Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Pathology 2020; 3(1): 30-33 DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.33545/pathol.2020.v3.i1a.150>

24. Matreja, *et al.* Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal | Volume 24 | Issue 4 |
October-December 2017 DOI: 10.4103/npmj.npmj_150_17
25. MN Nowsher *et al.* MN Nowsher *et al.* Mediscope 2023;10(1): 01-09, DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.3329/mediscope.v10i1.65397>